

Reactions of Titanium Alkoxides with N-ethylaminoethanols

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Titanium alkoxides react with N-ethylaminoethanols in stoichiometric ratios to give compounds with general formula, $(OR)_{4-n}Ti(OCH_2CH_2NR'R'')_n$ [R = Et and Prⁱ; R' = H, R'' = Et; R' = R'' = Et; n = 1-4]. Physical properties like molecular weight, infrared spectra and thermal stability are recorded. Reactions of tetrakisderivatives with phenylisocyanate and acetyl chloride are studied.

REACTIONS of aminoalcohols with a number of metal alkoxides¹⁻⁷ have been studied. We have already reported the reactions of titanium alkoxides⁸ with N-methylaminoalcohols, and the interesting results achieved encouraged us to extend the study with other substituted aminoalcohols like N-ethyl- and N-diethylaminoethanols. In this paper we report the preparation and some properties of N-ethylaminoalkoxides of titanium.

Experimental

All glass apparatus with interchangeable standard glass joints were used. N-ethylaminoalcohol (b.p., 167°) and N-diethylaminoalcohol (b.p., 163°) were purified by distillation. Phenyl isocyanate (b.p., 164°) and acetyl chloride (b.p., 51°-52°) were used after distillation. Solvents and alcohols were dried as usual.

Alcohols (ethanol and isopropanol) were estimated oxidimetrically¹². Titanium was estimated as TiO₂ by direct ignition after treating with ammonium hydroxide. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method. *Carbon and hydrogen analysis was done by C.S.I.R.O., Australia.* Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 with KBr plates. Molecular weights were determined on Gallenkamp ebulliometer.

1) Reactions of titanium alkoxides with N-ethylaminoalcohols :

To weighed amount of titanium alkoxide in ~ 80 ml benzene was added stoichiometric quantity of N-ethylaminoalcohol. Contents were refluxed for ~ 1½ hrs. Binary azeotrope (benzene-ethanol or benzene-isopropanol) was collected and analyzed for the alcohol content. Excess of the solvent was removed and compound was dried finally at ~ 30°/0.2 mm for ~ 2 hrs. Results are tabulated (Table 1).

2) Reactions of tetrakis derivatives, $Ti(OCH_2CH_2NR'R'')_4$ with phenylisocyanate in the molar ratio 1 : 4 :

To weighed amount of $Ti(OCH_2CH_2NR'R'')_4$ in ~10 ml benzene was added phenylisocyanate.

Reaction was found to be very exothermic. The contents were shaken and left for ½ hr. Excess of the solvent was removed and compound was dried at ~30°/0.2 mm for ~ 2 hrs. Results are summarised (Table 2).

3) Reactions of tetrakis derivatives, $Ti(OCH_2CH_2NR'R'')_4$ with acetyl chloride in the molar ratio 1 : 4 :

To a cooled solution of $Ti(OCH_2CH_2NR'R'')_4$ in ~40 ml chloroform was added acetyl chloride. Reaction was very exothermic and a black solid separates immediately. Contents were refluxed for ~1 hr. The black solid was filtered and washed with chloroform and dried (30°/0.2 mm) for ~ 2½ hrs.

From the filtrate the organic ester was isolated by distillation. The results are given in Table 2.

4) Hydrolysis of $Ti\left[-N\begin{matrix} Ph \\ CO.OCH_2CH_2NHEt \end{matrix}\right]_4$:

To a weighed amount of the compound (2.19 g) dissolved in dioxane was added excess water, when titanium hydroxide precipitates out. After filtering out the precipitate, the filtrate was concentrated and then water was added to it, when

a white solid crystallizes out, yield 60%. It was recrystallized from hot benzene (m.p. 122°), yield, 88%. Found : C, 63.49; H, 7.68; N, 13.44. Compound C₁₁H₁₆N₁O₂ requires C, 63.81; H, 7.67; N, 13.45%.

5) Hydrolysis of $Ti\left[-N\begin{matrix} Ph \\ CO.OCH_2CH_2NEt_2 \end{matrix}\right]_4$:

To a weighed amount of the compound (1.99 g) in dioxane was added excess water. Details are as

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF TITANIUM ALKOXIDES WITH N-ETHYLAMINOETHANOLS

Srl. No.	Reactants (g)		Molar ratio	Alcohol in azeotrope Found (Calcd.)	Yield (%)	Nature of product	Analysis (%)		Molecular complexity
	Titanium iso-propoxide	N-diethyl-amino-ethanol					Ti Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	
1.	2.231	0.928	1 : 1	0.44 (0.47)	99	Yellow viscous liquid (OPr ⁱ) ₃ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂)	14.60 (14.00)	4.06 (4.08)	0.97
2.	1.414	1.164	1 : 2	0.46 (0.57)	98	Yellow viscous liquid (OPr ⁱ) ₂ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₂	12.21 (12.03)	7.02 (7.03)	—
3.	2.504	3.236	1 : 3	1.44 (1.50)	99	Yellow viscous liquid (OPr ⁱ)Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₃	10.40 (10.53)	9.20 (9.23)	—
4.	1.558	2.554	1 : 4	0.92 (1.00)	92	Yellow viscous liquid Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₄	9.70 (9.36)	10.94 (10.96)	—
<i>N-ethylaminoethanol</i>									
5.	2.166	0.679	1 : 1	0.45 (0.45)	95	Yellow viscous liquid (OPr ⁱ) ₃ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET)	15.50 (15.29)	4.41 (4.46)	1.00
6.	1.937	1.215	1 : 2	0.63 (0.79)	94	Yellow viscous liquid (OPr ⁱ) ₂ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET) ₂	14.23 (13.99)	8.16 (8.17)	1.00
7.	3.160	2.974	1 : 3	1.95 (1.99)	100	Yellow viscous liquid (OPr ⁱ)Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET) ₃	13.11 (12.90)	11.30 (11.31)	—
8.	1.570	1.970	1 : 4	1.21 (1.32)	98	Yellow viscous liquid Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET) ₄	11.84 (11.69)	13.71 (13.98)	—
<i>Ti(OEt)₄</i>									
9.	1.742	0.682	1 : 1	0.35 (0.35)	99	Yellow viscous liquid (OEt) ₃ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET)	17.14 (17.66)	5.14 (5.15)	—
10.	1.491	1.165	1 : 2	0.59 (0.60)	98	Yellow viscous liquid (OEt) ₂ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET) ₂	15.30 (15.15)	8.75 (8.91)	—
11.	2.107	2.469	1 : 3	1.26 (1.27)	98	Yellow viscous liquid (OEt)Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHET) ₃	13.75 (13.59)	11.74 (11.75)	—
<i>N-diethylaminoethanol</i>									
12.	1.592	0.818	1 : 1	0.28 (0.32)	98	Red viscous liquid (OEt) ₃ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂)	16.07 (16.01)	4.59 (4.61)	—
13.	1.829	1.889	1 : 2	0.66 (0.73)	98	Red viscous liquid (OEt) ₂ Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₂	13.17 (12.93)	7.52 (7.55)	—
14.	2.071	3.200	1 : 3	1.00 (1.25)	99	Red viscous liquid (OEt)Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₃	11.02 (10.85)	9.45 (9.51)	—

above. White solid was obtained, yield, 60%. It was recrystallized from benzene (m.p. 98°), yield, 80%. Found: N, 11.83. Compound C₁₃H₂₁NO₂ requires N, 11.85%.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of titanium alkoxides, Ti(OR)₄, (R = Et and Prⁱ) with N-ethylaminoethanols, HOCH₂CH₂NR'R'', in different molar ratios can be represented as follows:

(R = Et and Prⁱ; R' = H, R'' = Et; R' = R'' = Et; n = 1-4).

The alcohol (ethanol or isopropanol) produced in the reaction could be fractionated and analysed. As derivatives of N-methylaminoalcohols⁸ could be distilled unchanged under reduced pressure, attempts were made to distil the above derivatives also. Almost all the products appeared to be stable to heat upto a temperature about 270-300° under a pressure of ~0.2 mm, after which they underwent sensitive decomposition yielding a charred product. The mono-, (OPrⁱ)₃Ti(OCH₂CH₂NR'R'') [R' = H, R'' = Et; R' = R'' = Et] and di-derivatives, (OPrⁱ)₂Ti(OCH₂CH₂NHET)₂, appear to disproportionate at much lower temperatures yielding titanium iso-propoxide at ~ 60°/0.2 mm.

Titanium ethoxide and isopropoxide have been reported to show average degree of molecular association⁹ of 2.4 and 1.4 respectively in refluxing benzene. Determination of molecular weight (ebullioscopically in benzene) of these derivatives showed (Table 2) that even the mono-substituted derivatives,

TABLE 2—REACTIONS OF TETRA-ETHYLAMINOALKOXIDES WITH PHENYLISOCYANATE AND ACETYLCHLORIDE

Srl. No.	Reactants (g) Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₄	PhNCO	Molar ratio	Yield (%)	Nature of product	Analysis (%)		
						Ti Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	Cl Found (Calcd.)
1.	1.392	1.290	1:4	98	Yellow solid Ti-[N<Ph CO.O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂] ₄	4.97 (4.84)	11.44 (11.32)	—
	Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHEt) ₄							
2.	1.400	1.666	1:4	99	Yellow solid Ti-[N<Ph CO.O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHEt] ₄	5.22 (5.46)	12.57 (12.78)	—
	Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂) ₄	Acetylchloride						
3.	2.9071	1.984	1:4	94	Brown pasty soluble solid TiCl ₄ .2CH ₃ C(=O).CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂	9.40 (9.34)	5.45 (5.46)	27.16 (27.70)
	Ti(O.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHEt) ₄			60	White liquid CH ₃ C(=O).CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NEt ₂ (b.p., 100°C).	—	8.66 (8.70)	—
4.	2.390	1.864	1:4	98	Brown insoluble solid TiCl ₄ .2CH ₃ C(=O).CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHEt	10.58 (10.59)	6.19 (6.22)	31.05 (31.42)
				62	White liquid CH ₃ C(=O).CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NHEt (b.p., 95°C).	—	10.57 (10.68)	—

Ti(OPrⁱ)₃(OCH₂CH₂NR'R''), appear to behave as monomeric species. This abrupt change to monomeric state can be taken to be an indication of the chelating behaviour of ethylaminoethoxy group. Similar to the N-Dimethylamino-alkoxy derivatives, the N-diethylamino-alkoxy derivatives of titanium have also been found to be monomeric. However, in contrast to the monomeric N-ethylamino-alkoxy derivatives (mono and bis-), the corresponding N-methylamino-alkoxy derivatives have been found to be dimeric. It appears, therefore, that even under these chelating conditions, the size of the substituent alkyl group at nitrogen affects the molecular complexity of the products and the N-methylamino-alkoxy derivatives can associate further probably through alkoxy bridges.

The compounds (No. 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11) show medium to strong band at 3125–3226 cm⁻¹ assignable to N-H. Ti-O stretchings can be made noted in all these amino-alkoxy derivatives in the range 630–480 cm⁻¹.

Insertion reactions of titanium alkoxides¹⁰ have been studied recently. It has been found during

this work that tetra-derivatives, Ti(OCH₂CH₂NR'R'')₄, add readily to phenylisocyanate in the following manner:

(R' = H, R'' = Et; R' = R'' = Et).

The disappearance of the band at 2250 cm⁻¹ (arising due to N = C = O) in these products clearly indicates that insertion occurs at νN = C. This is further supported by the presence of νC = O at 1700 cm⁻¹. Moreover, in the 630–480 cm⁻¹ region the typical Ti-O stretchings of aminoalkoxy compounds are replaced by sharp phenyl deformations. The products are extremely prone to hydrolysis and on treatment with water in dioxane yield the expected organic residue, HN(Ph)COOCH₂CH₂NR'R'', which

could be identified by carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses and IR spectra.

Ti-O bond of the tetra-derivative get cleaved with acetyl chloride resulting into 1 : 2 adducts of tetra-chloride as follows :

These adducts are found to be insoluble and from its filtrate, the organic ester could be distilled out and characterised.

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